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Title: Replication of previous genome-wide association studies of psychiatric diseases in a large schizophrenia case-control sample from Spain

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Abstract: Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) has allowed the discovery of some interesting risk variants for schizophrenia (SCZ). However, this high-throughput approach presents some limitations, being the most important the necessity of highly restrictive statistical corrections as well as the loss of statistical power inherent to the use of a Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNP) analysis approach. These problems can be partially solved through the use of a polygenic approach. We performed a genotyping study in SCZ using 86 previously associated SNPs identified by GWAS of SCZ, bipolar disorder (BPD) and autistic spectrum disorders (ASD) patients. The sample consisted of 3063 independent cases with DSM-IV-TR diagnosis of SCZ and 2847 independent controls of European origin from Spain. A polygenic score analysis was also used to test the overall effect on the SCZ status. One SNPs, rs12290811, located in the ODZ4 gene reached statistical significance ($P = 1.7 \times 10^{-4}$, Allelic Odds Ratio = 1.21), a value very near to those reported in previous GWAS of BPD patients. In addition, 4 SNPs were close to the significant threshold: rs3850333, in the NRXN1 gene; rs6932590, at MHC; rs2314398, located in an intergenic region on chromosome 2; and rs1006737, in the CACNA1C gene. We also found that 74% of the studied SNPs showed the same tendency (risk or protection alleles) previously reported in the original GWAS ($P < 0.001$). Our data strengthen the polygenic component of susceptibility to SCZ. Our findings show ODZ4 as a risk gene for SCZ, emphasizing the existence of common vulnerability in psychosis.

Authors JLI, OR, JC MDM and JS designed the study and managed the literature searches. MA, RR-R, AC. TP, RR-J, JC, BG, EM, CA, MA, JCP, VP, PAS, MPG-P, JB, AG-P, IZ, JMH, MB, EB-G, JCG, JH, and JS provided the samples of this study. JC and AC managed genotyping. JLI, JC and RI undertook the statistical analysis. JLI, OR and RI wrote the first draft of the manuscript. JC, JH, MDM and JS reviewed the manuscript draft. All authors contributed to and have approved the final manuscript.

1. Introduction

The common disease/common variant (CDCV) hypothesis posits that genetic vulnerability to common complex disorders is mainly due to common genetic variants, which have a modest effect on the disease risk and are shared by different subpopulations. The additive effect of these low-risk variants, together with environmental factors and their interactions, will therefore cause the disease (Reich and Lander, 2001; Risch and Merikangas, 1996). Thus, the search for these common risk variants has led to the development of genome-wide association studies (GWAS), hypothesis-free association studies that allow the testing of several thousand single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) simultaneously (Wellcome Trust Case Control Consortium, 2007). However, the success of finding risk variants for common disorders can only be understood through the use of several large, representative samples of patients and controls.

The development of GWAS has been particularly fruitful in the field of psychiatric genetics, as they have spurred the development of new hypotheses and the identification of new pathways potentially involved in these diseases. Specifically, GWAS have identified common genetic variations related to schizophrenia (SCZ) (Stefansson et al. 2009), bipolar disorder (BPD) (Sklar et al. 2008), and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (Weiss and Arking, 2009), which meet modern standards for replication and significance. Genome-wide genetic approaches generate a large amount of data that can be used for comparisons and to search for risk variants for different neuropsychiatric conditions with shared etiological factors, such as SCZ, BPD, and ASD (O'Donovan et al, 2009; Sullivan et al. 2012). This has been the case for SCZ and BPD (International Schizophrenia Consortium et al. 2009), where some common risk factors for these disorders have been found using GWAS (Ferreira et al. 2008; O'Donovan et al. 2008; Steinberg et al. 2014; Williams et al. 2011). Regarding the relationship between ASD and other neuropsychiatric disorders, evidence of shared genetic risk factors has been published in copy number variation studies, with *NRXN1* among the most interesting candidates (O'Donovan et al. 2009).

Based on the results of GWAS for neuropsychiatric disorders, a number of candidate genes have been suggested, but additional replication in several independent samples is

required to verify the original findings. Nevertheless, GWAS present some disadvantages and difficulties. The most common analysis in GWAS is to perform independent associations for each SNP. However, this approach has several flaws. One of them is that the need for corrections due to multiple rounds of testing for thousands of SNPs sets a very low and restrictive significance threshold. Furthermore, putative low-risk variants are likely to interact with each other to influence the phenotype; therefore, an independent analysis of each SNP most likely causes a loss of power to detect their effects. The genetic etiology of some common diseases could be explained by exploring a number of variants simultaneously (Valdar et al. 2006). For psychiatric disorders, this can be carried out with a polygenic approach (International Schizophrenia Consortium et al. 2009).

The objective of this work is to analyze in a large and homogenous (all of European origin from Spain) sample of patients with schizophrenia, the most significant polymorphisms that have been associated with psychosis (SCZ, BPD) and autism in previous GWAS. The advantage of this approach is that a relatively small number of tests are needed in comparison with traditional GWAS.

2. Methods

2.1. Samples

The study consisted of 2847 DNA control samples (57% males) and 3063 DNA samples from patients with the diagnosis of SCZ (56% males). The statistical power to detect positive results, calculated with Quanto software (Gauderman and Morrison, 2006), was between 42% and 98% (Supplementary Figure 1). All the samples were taken from the Spanish National DNA Bank of the Spanish National Network for Research in Mental Health CIBERSAM. The samples came from 11 different research groups (Supplementary Table 1). The mean age was 43.61 ± 15.54 (range: 17-91) for the control samples and 39.04 ± 29.50 (range: 14-87) for the case samples. All patients met the DSM-IV-TR criteria for SCZ diagnosis. The assessment methods in patients and controls are indicated in Table S1. All the individuals involved in this study gave their written consent for this study. The study was approved by the ethics committee of each group's institution.

2.2. SNP selection and genotyping

A total of 95 SNPs were selected from 19 previous GWAS published between 2007 and 2009 on SCZ, BPD, and ASD. GWAS were selected using the Schizophrenia Gene Database and Pubmed (Supplementary Table 2).

The SNP selection criteria were (i) minor allele frequency >0.1 and (ii) the most significant SNPs in each study, including not only the genome-wide significant SNPs but also the significant SNPs close to the threshold. These 95 SNPs were used as the input for Spectro DESIGNER software (Sequenom, San Diego, CA, USA) to generate multiplex assays for genotyping. Twenty SNPs were discarded by the above-mentioned tool or presented a low likelihood of successful design according to the software, and these were replaced by linked SNPs with $r^2 > 0.8$ in the HapMap samples from Utah (USA) residents with northern and western European ancestry (CEU). By using this strategy, a total of 86 SNPs were included in three high-level multiplexes (Supplementary Table 2) and were genotyped using the iPLEX MassARRAY technology from Sequenom. The results were manually inspected to confirm genotype assignments. Exclusion criteria for the SNPs were the following: (i) a genotyping call rate lower than 95%, (ii) a significant difference in call rates between cases and control subjects ($p < 0.05$), and (iii) departure from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) in control samples ($p < 0.05$). As a genotyping quality control, two trios from the Coriell Institute included within the HapMap CEU samples were genotyped. There were no Mendelian inconsistencies, and all genotypes were consistent with HapMap data.

2.3. Control for population stratification

In the Spanish population, no stratification has been detected, except in the Canary Islands (Gayán et al. 2010; Laayouni et al. 2010). No individuals from the Canary Islands were included in this study (Table S1). Therefore, genetic association studies in our sample have a minor risk of population stratification. Nevertheless, as an additional control, a subset of 5365 samples was genotyped for 47 ancestry-informative markers using the Sequenom MassARRAY. Structure 2.3.1 software (Pritchard et al. 2000; <http://pritch.bsd.uchicago.edu/structure.html>) was used under the admixture model with 50,000 replications for the burn-in period for parameter estimations to estimate the percentage of European ancestry using the HapMap CEU and Yoruba in Ibadan, Nigeria (YRI) populations. A combination of the HapMap Han Chinese in Beijing (CHB) and

Japanese in Tokyo (JPT) populations were used as references. Samples showing less than 90% European ancestry were removed from the analysis.

2.4. Statistical analysis

HWE was tested using Pearson's goodness-of-fit chi-square test. Plink (Purcell et al. 2007; <http://pngu.mgh.harvard.edu/purcell/plink/>) and R software (Development Core Team, 2008) were used to independently analyze the SNPs by logistic regression, with five tested genetic models: trend test, allelic, codominant, recessive, and dominant. The threshold p-value, after Bonferroni correction, was 2.7×10^{-4} . This value took into account the number of polymorphisms analyzed and the different models of inheritance, with an effective number of 2.2 tests according to Gonzalez et al. (2008). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to compare the trend of our results (protective or susceptibility allele) with those obtained in the previous GWAS.

2.5. Polygenic model

Due to the nature of our study design, all the polymorphisms had been previously associated with SCZ, ASD, or BPD, so a polygenic score analysis was also used to test the overall effect on the SCZ status. The trend of the association in our samples was also compared with the original studies to check for similarities.

To construct a polygenic model, first the log odds ratios for each individual SNP in a training data set were calculated. Second, the obtained values were applied to another independent test data set to ascertain if an increased number of SNPs could better explain heritability (International Schizophrenia Consortium et al. 2009). We constructed polygenic scoring classifiers for our SCZ data. By means of a resampling approach, the whole sample was randomly and repeatedly split into halves as the training and testing samples. The log odds ratios and the p-values were computed for each specific SNP in the training sample fitting a log-additive model. For this purpose, each SNP value was coded regarding the number of risk alleles the individual carried: 0, 1, or 2. Subsequently, a polygenic score for each subject in the testing sample was constructed by taking the sum of the products between each log odds ratio and the number of risk alleles carried by each individual SNP. A series of significance ranges for SNP association p-values in the training dataset that were included in the polygenic classifier were tested over the testing sample (0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8,

0.9, and 1). Moreover, the ranges excluding the most significant findings (0.05-0.2, 0.05-0.5, and 0.2-0.5) were checked to explore a possible common polygenic inheritance model for these SNPs. The procedure was performed 1000 times, and the performance of the polygenic scoring classifier in each testing dataset was evaluated with an increasing number of SNPs. The association between polygenic score and case control status was assessed by analyzing the distribution of p-values for the logistic regression models applied over the test data sets. The prediction capability was assessed by computing the average of the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve obtained for each interaction.

3. Results

3.1. Quality control procedures

The mean genotyping call rate was 96.4% (SD 1.26%), with all SNPs having a genotyping call rate higher than 95%. Among the samples, no significant differences in the genotyping call rate (t-test: $p=0.12$) were found when the cases (96.48%) and control subjects (96.31%) were compared.

Two SNPs, rs4771136 and rs4974096, were not in HWE in the control sample and therefore were excluded from the rest of our analysis. A total of 163 samples (64 controls and 99 patients) were excluded because they had less than 90% European ancestry or had a genotyping call rate less than 95%. Thus, 2783 controls and 2964 patients composed the final sample.

3.2. Association analysis

All the polymorphisms had minor allele frequencies similar to those reported previously. One of the 84 SNPs (rs12290811) reached significance (trend test $p=1.7 \times 10^{-4}$, Table 1, Figure 1). The odds ratio associated with the rs12290811 minor allele as 1.21 (95% confidence interval: 1.13-1.49), a value close to those reported in previous BPD GWAS (Ferreira et al. 2008; Psychiatric GWAS Consortium Bipolar Disorder Working Group, 2011). This SNP is located in intron 1 of the *ODZ4* gene (chromosome 11q14.1) that is also known as *TENM4* (*Teneurin transmembrane protein 4*).

We also found four SNPs that were close to the significance threshold (Table 1). They were rs3850333, located in the *NRXN1* (*Neurexin-1*) gene ($p=3 \times 10^{-3}$); rs6932590, located in the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) ($p=4 \times 10^{-3}$); rs2314398, located in an intergenic region on chromosome 2 ($p=5 \times 10^{-3}$); and rs1006737, located in the *CACNA1C* (*Calcium channel, voltage-dependent, L type, alpha 1C subunit*) gene ($p=6 \times 10^{-3}$).

The association results for the 84 SNPs are shown in Supplementary Table 3 considering the codominant genetic model. We observed that 74% of the studied SNPs showed the same risk tendency (risk or protection alleles) previously reported in the original association studies, ($p < 0.001$). This trend reached 100% in those SNPs with p values below 0.05 in our sample.

3.3. Polygenic model

As shown in Table 2 when expanding the p -value threshold and, therefore, increasing the number of SNPs included in the polygenic model, p -values for the log odds ratio of association between the polygenic score and SCZ decreased from 0.30 to 0.16. However, the constructed polygenic score did not show statistical significance for any range. In addition to the diminution of score p -values, the percentage of simulations having a score with $p < 0.05$ was maximum over a threshold of 0.7. Regarding the predictive assessment, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) increased as the p -value range was expanded (Figure 2), suggesting a better predictive power for the polygenic score as the number of SNPs increased. Although all area under the curve values ranged from 0.51 to 0.53 and all of them were significantly different from 0.5, the low values suggest that the polygenic score had a low power to predict case-control status. Values for score prediction are given in Figure 2 and Table 2. Table 2 also shows the number of SNPs included in each score. It increased as the p -value range was expanded. Smaller ranges had higher p -values and lower AUC values. If there had been no association between the SNPs and the disease, the p -value distribution might have been random; but, as shown in Supplementary Figure 2, for ranges including significant SNPs, the distribution of the p -value frequency for the association between the polygenic score and the disease among simulations followed a non-random pattern.

4. Discussion

In this study, we identified an association between rs12290811 and SCZ in a large sample of Spanish patients. This polymorphism is located in the *ODZA* gene, and both *ODZA* and rs12290811 have been consistently associated with BPD (Ferreira et al. 2008; Green, 2013; Psychiatric GWAS Consortium Bipolar Disorder Working Group, 2011). Therefore, *ODZA* is one of the most robust BPD susceptibility genes.

ODZA encodes a member of the teneurins (teneurin-4), a group of type II transmembrane glycoproteins with an important role in neuronal development (Young and Leamey, 2009). *ODZA* seems to act as a signaling molecule during gastrulation, as shown in mice (Lossie et al. 2005), as well as in oligodendrocyte differentiation and myelination (Suzuki et al. 2012). This gene has a tissue-specific expression, including adult brain and fetal brain (Nagase et al. 2000; Suzuki et al. 2012). The polymorphism rs12290811 is located in intron 1 of *ODZA*, and according to the ENCODE project (ENCODE Project Consortium, 2011), it might be situated within a DNase I hypersensitive site. These sites are regions of accessible chromatin related to transcriptional activity and constitute markers of regulatory DNA. Interestingly, the ancestral allele of rs12290811 (allele T) is conserved in a high number of analyzed vertebrate species, especially in mammals (UCSC Genome Browser on Human Feb. 2009 (GRCh37/hg19) Assembly, <http://www.encodeproject.org/>). Therefore, intron 1 of *ODZA* might contain a regulatory sequence where this polymorphism is located, meaning each allele might contribute differentially to the expression of this gene. Alternatively, other genes could be under the control of the putative *ODZA* intron 1 regulatory sequence, contributing to the vulnerability to SCZ. Further investigation is needed to define the functional relevance of the intron 1 sequence of *ODZA*.

In addition, it should be noted that two microRNA (miRNA) loci (miR-708 and miR-5579) are located in *ODZA* intron 1. miRNAs regulate gene expression by attaching to mRNA strands of target genes, and they are crucial in the development of the central nervous system (Meza-Sosa et al. 2012). Both miR-708 and *ODZA* are highly expressed in the mouse brain (Behrman et al. 2011), suggesting common physiological functions in this tissue. miR-708 is involved in the homeostatic regulation of endoplasmic reticulum stress in mammalian rod photoreceptors (Behrman et al. 2011), and it is also

involved in different cancer-related processes (Saini et al. 2011; Ryu et al. 2013). Because each miRNA has the ability to target and regulate a diverse set of genes, it is probable that the function of miR-708 depends on the expressing tissue and might target genes associated with SCZ in the brain. Indeed, potential targets of miR-708 listed in the miR-Ontology database (<http://ferrolab.dmi.unict.it/miro/>) are genes previously associated with SCZ and BPD: *XBPI* (X-box-binding protein 1), *Timeless* (Timeless homolog), *PAFAH1B1* (platelet-activating factor acetylhydrolase, isoform 1B, alpha subunit), *RGS4* (regulator of G-protein signaling 4), *NCAM1* (neural cell adhesion molecule 1), and *ATXN1* (ataxin 1). Whether the polymorphism rs12290811 affects a regulatory sequence of *ODZ4*, it might also affect the expression of the mir-708 since this microRNA cotranscribed with its host gene (Behrman et al. 2011). Therefore variation in the expression of mir-708 may alter the expression of multiple target genes, which is compatible with a polygenic origin of SCZ.

In this study, we found other SNPs close to the significance threshold. Especially interesting is rs1006737, which is located in the *CACNA1C* gene and is strongly associated with SCZ and BPD (Cross-Disorder Group of the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium, Genetic Risk Outcome of Psychosis (GROUP) Consortium, 2013; Ferreira et al. 2008; Hamshere et al. 2013; Nyegaard et al. 2010). *CACNA1C* encodes the alpha-1 subunit of the L-type voltage-gated calcium channel, and it plays a key role in the development and function of both the central nervous system and the cardiovascular system. Genetic variants of *CACNA1C* have also been associated with poor executive function (Soeiro-de-Souza et al., 2013) as well as alterations in prefrontal activation and fronto-hippocampal connectivity (Paulus et al. 2013). Another SNP close to the significance threshold is located in the *NRXN1* gene. Neurexins are pre-synaptic neural adhesion molecules of great importance in the formation and maintenance of synapses. Accordingly variations in *NRXN1*, particularly copy number variations, have been associated with risk of SCZ or ASD (Kim et al. 2008; Kirov et al. 2009; Morrow et al. 2008; Rujescu et al., 2009), thus bridging a gap between these disorders. Finally, we also found a SNP located in the MHC region that was close to the significance threshold. In fact, one of the most consistent findings in GWAS of SCZ is the strong genetic association of the MHC (Stefansson et al. 2009), a region that encodes the classical human leukocyte antigen genes and many other genes involved in immune function, cellular processes, and nervous system development and function.

The possibility of a common genetic vulnerability for SCZ and other mental disorders is an emerging topic (Carroll and Owen, 2009). Recently a large study using samples from five different mental disorders, including SCZ, BPD, and ASD, found that specific SNPs may be associated with different psychopathologies (Cross-Disorder Group of the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium, Genetic Risk Outcome of Psychosis (GROUP) Consortium, 2013). Moreover, hippocampal abnormalities are one of the main features in SCZ, but this feature may be shared by BPD patients (Hulshoff Pol et al. 2012). BPD and SCZ have been traditionally assessed as different clinical entities, but our results support the hypothesis of shared susceptibility alleles for both disorders.

Risk alleles of *ODZ4* and other genes (such as *CACNAC1*) could slightly alter different pathways of the nervous system, conferring a susceptibility to develop mental disease. This hypothesis needs additional testing, starting with the search for the causative alleles. The polymorphism rs12290811 is located in intron 1 of *ODZ4*, and it might affect a regulatory region.

In this study, data mining techniques were used to test whether the accumulation of previously associated polymorphisms could better explain the occurrence of a disease. These data mining methods have successfully been used for SCZ (Carrera et al. 2012; International Schizophrenia Consortium et al. 2009), and other diseases (Simonson et al. 2011; Wang et al. 2011). The findings of our polygenic model, when applied to the SCZ data, agree with the International Schizophrenia Consortium results and suggest that an increasing number of SNPs could increase the power to explain its heritability. The fact that 74% of the SNPs show the same direction of effect as the original publication strongly suggests that many of them are true susceptibility SNPs. However, our polygenic model is not significant and must be interpreted cautiously. Complex diseases may arise from a huge number of genetic and environmental factors, and this study only analyzes a small number of SNPs at the top of the range of significance values in previous GWAS. This strongly suggests the existence of many additional susceptibility SNPs embedded within the whole distribution of significance values. Moreover, rare alleles (Xu et al. 2011) and copy number variations (Walsh et al. 2008) may play important roles in SCZ, and therefore, the CDCV hypothesis cannot completely explain the etiology of this disease. This genetic architecture, together with the importance of environmental factors, greatly decreases the statistical power of the polygenic model.

Nevertheless, this approach seems to have an important heuristic value for analyzing future GWAS or for reanalyzing previous studies including very large samples.

In conclusion, this study suggests that *ODZ4* polymorphisms, previously related to BPD, may have a role in pathways involved in the pathogenesis of SCZ. One of the weaknesses of this study is the limited number of analyzed polymorphisms in the sample. However, this limitation is also strength because it allowed us to increase our power to detect differences in comparison with traditional GWAS. We have used a small set of SNPs with a high *a priori* probability of being associated with the disorder. Moreover, our sample is also ethnically very homogenous, which avoids possible biases. Finally, our study has the value of being an independent replication of large GWAS on SCZ, which is necessary for the confirmation of those previous findings.

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Manhattan plot displaying the analysis results using an allelic model. Dotted line represents the p-value-threshold.

Figure 2. Average of the area under the Receiving Operating Characteristic curves (AUC) for prediction with polygenic score approach including different SNPs regarding p-value ranges of association between SNPs and schizophrenia. Bars represent the 95% Confidence Interval for each average.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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Table 1. Main results of the association study

SNP	Chromosome	Gene	OR	P-value
rs12290811	11	<i>ODZ4</i>	1.21	1.7x10⁻⁴
rs3850333	2	<i>NRX1</i>	0.91	3x10 ⁻³
rs6932590	6	<i>MHC</i>	0.89	4x10 ⁻³
rs2314398	2	Intergenic	0.92	5x10 ⁻³
rs1006737	12	<i>CACNA1C</i>	1.12	6x10 ⁻³

Values in bold represent SNPs below the p-value threshold from the logistic regression analysis (trend test). The Odds Ratio (OR) value is given according to the minor allele.

Table 2. Description of the values obtained for each range of SNP association p-values

SNP p-value range	N SNPs in score	score p-values	% p <0.05	AUC	
				average	CI 95%
(0,0.05)	6	0.3030859	21.4	0.5125741	(0.5119,0.5132)
(0,0.1)	20	0.2406858	26.9	0.5178998	(0.5173,0.5185)
(0,0.2)	20	0.2450132	29.8	0.5177795	(0.5171,0.5185)
(0,0.3)	29	0.2226611	32.9	0.5199144	(0.5192,0.5207)
(0,0.4)	37	0.2331008	27.4	0.520173	(0.5195,0.5209)
(0,0.5)	45	0.2037139	33.9	0.5225205	(0.5218,0.5233)
(0,0.6)	53	0.2013924	34.4	0.5236053	(0.5228,0.5244)
(0,0.7)	62	0.1850717	37.6	0.525349	(0.5246,0.5261)
(0,0.8)	70	0.1783110	40.7	0.5257768	(0.5250,0.5266)
(0,0.9)	78	0.1797875	38.5	0.5264736	(0.5257,0.5273)
1	86	0.1639335	40.2	0.5275439	(0.5267,0.5284)
(0.05,0.2)	14	0.3860197	15	0.5103261	(0.5095,0.5111)
(0.05,0.5)	39	0.3665081	15.3	0.5135795	(0.5128,0.5144)
(0.2,0.5)	25	0.4630576	7.8	0.5064388	(0.5057,0.5072)

The number of SNPs (N) included in the polygenic model, the p-value of the log odds ratio for the polygenic score and the percentage of p-values which were under 0.05 threshold for 1000 resampling iterations are shown; AUC, Area under de receiver operating characteristic curves for polygenic model prediction; CI, confidence interval.

Figure 1
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Figure 2

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